

Theory of natural evolution of all things

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Abstract: This article systematically explores the existence of our world, the evolution laws of all things in nature, and analyzes the emergence process and principles of various phenomena. Firstly, this article discusses the existence phenomena of ontology, entity, and subject, and provides conceptual definitions. Subsequently, this article analyzed various self-organizing phenomena in the evolution process of entities, explored how everything evolved from its basic structure, and analyzed and summarized the forms and laws of evolution at each stage. Meanwhile, this article explores how intelligence and consciousness emerge during the evolution process, as well as the development trend of intelligent communities. This article provides a systematic exploration and analysis of the evolution process of all things in nature, which has practical significance for promoting philosophical research on the essence of the world for humanity.

Keywords: Ontology; Existence; Entity; Evolution; Cell; Consciousness; Intelligence; Metaverse

I. The theory of existence

1. Ontology

The definition of ontology: Ontology refers to the eternal, definite, and unique ultimate existence that encompasses all things existing in the spatial and temporal dimensions.

The Infinity of Ontology: Ontology has infinity, encompassing all possible existences and variations.

Evolutionary nature of ontology: The internal elements of ontology can form different forms, and its internal structure can undergo complex changes in the time dimension.

2. Entity theory

Definition of entity: An entity is a structure of continuous differences in different dimensions of a large spatiotemporal ontology.

The existence of entities: The essence of the existence of entities lies in their

differences. Differentiation is a manifestation of the concept of existence, without differences there is no existence.

Interactivity of entities: The relationship between entities and systems is continuous, and the form of entities and the form of the relationship between systems have a mutual influence, which is called basic interaction.

Subjectivity of Entity: The existence of an entity is equivalent to the existence of its subject. The essence of subject existence lies in its interactivity, and the form of subject existence is the content of its subject perspective, that is, its subjective content.

3. Subjectivity theory

The definition of subject perspective: In an infinite dimensional ontology system, each entity has a specific subject perspective, and the content changes of this perspective correspond to the changes in the entity structure.

Subjectivity of the subjective perspective: The changes in the content of the subjective perspective map to external changes, and are manifested as subjective experiences in the subjective perspective of conscious subjects.

The authenticity of the subject perspective: The subject perspective is the only real existence perceived by the entity. The content of the subjective perspective is different from the objective perspective of the third party, which is an abstract simulation of the entity, while the former is the only real existence that the entity can sense.

II. Theory of Evolution

The evolution process of entities: from basic interactions to mirror universe systems.

The evolution mechanism of entities: The evolution process of entities is a continuous development process, which extends from basic interactions to super intelligent agents, and each stage is a natural extension of the previous stage. The characteristics and driving mechanisms of each stage determine the possibility and direction of its evolution towards higher stages.

The evolutionary characteristics of entities: The evolutionary characteristics of entities

lie in the improvement of adaptability. The essence of self evolving change is the continuous evolution and development of highly adaptive negative feedback structures under natural competition, with the direction of simulating the complexity of natural changes and preparing as early as possible to cope with changes.

Stage 1: Natural Basic Material Evolution Process: Basic Interactions Evolve to Form Self Organizing Material Structures

Entity structure: Basic material structure

Entity phenomena: forming complex vibration systems from micro to macro scales.

Evolutionary mechanism: The fundamental interactions determined by the characteristics of the spatiotemporal field.

Driving principle: Natural basic interactions drive entity combinations through spatiotemporal field characteristics to form more complex systems.

The form of Self-organizing

Self expanding form: The basic material structure is based on spontaneous attraction and repulsion, and continuously expands its own structure spontaneously.

Self replication form: The self expanding material structure achieves self replication and structural expansion through spontaneous attraction and repulsion.

Stage 2: Adaptive structure evolution process: self-organizing evolution forms an adaptive structure

Entity structure: Single cell self-organizing structure

Entity phenomena: adaptive, relying on multi steady state structure and negative feedback regulation.

Evolutionary mechanism: The composite physical effects of the profit seeking and harm avoiding characteristics of composite structures are more conducive to survival.

Driving principle: Single cell self-organizing structures achieve self adaptation and self maintenance through a complex physical effect of seeking benefits and avoiding harm.

The form of Adaptive

The sensing form of an entity: If an entity can perceive the interaction input of the environmental system, match multiple types of internal structures, and output

interactions, then this entity is an independent sensing entity structure.

Adaptive form of entity: If the sensing mode of an independent sensing entity structure can maintain its structural stability and continuity, then it is an adaptive system.

The self-organizing form of entities: If an adaptive system can continuously evolve towards a specific form direction, it is considered a self-organizing system with formal goals.

Stage 3: Natural Training Collaborative Structure Evolution Process: Adaptive Structure Collaborative Feedback Experience Evolution to Form Intelligent System

Entity structure: Multi cell collaborative aggregation intelligent agent

Entity phenomena: Cell aggregation, collaborative feedback of individual cell aggregation, forming a unified overall feedback intelligent system.

Evolutionary mechanism: Natural training of multi cell combination structures to form experience is beneficial for survival.

Driving principle: Multi cell collaborative aggregates form an experience driven unified collaborative feedback mechanism through natural training.

The form of Intelligent

The intelligent form of entities: A self-organizing system with goals can be considered an intelligent system if it has the ability to understand and transform the environment.

The universal intelligent form of entities: If an intelligent system has the ability to understand and transform knowledge through free association, it can be regarded as a universal intelligent system.

Stage 4: Consciousness Unified Subjective Evolution Process: Cell Network Evolution Forming Consciousness Attention Unified Subjective Content Pattern System

Entity structure: cellular network subject perspective, unified consciousness, intelligent agent

Entity phenomena: Consciousness feedback system, where the cellular network forms a unified consciousness feedback system through the mechanism of conscious attention.

Evolutionary mechanism: The attention mechanism in the consciousness neural

network is associated with sensing emotions, memory experiences, and forming a holistic response that is beneficial for survival.

Driving principle: External changes form the maximum emotional drive for overall response through attention mechanism and form a memory cycle iteration.

The form of consciousness

The definition of consciousness: Consciousness is the change in content that occurs from the perspective of the subject. Consciousness generally refers to the conscious state of animals that can be directly perceived. In animals with explicit consciousness, the content changes of the neural network entities on which explicit consciousness relies from the perspective of subjectivity are the explicit consciousness itself. This neural network can not only recognize the characteristics of external changes, but also simulate the things that affect it from a subjective perspective.

The mechanism of consciousness

The operation process of consciousness: The consciousness neural network unifies various reflex arc neural networks to form a unified maximum reflex direction response to external changes. The attention model in the consciousness neural network selects the most activated sensory network, the experiential memory model predicts changes experienced based on emotional mapping memory, the conceptual understanding model actively predicts unknown changes, the regularity model has the best judgment of comparative experience, the principle system model has systematic causal logic, and the panoramic reflection framework has self referential and consistent completeness.

The Value of Consciousness

The individual value of consciousness: Consciousness is not just a passive response to current stimuli, but an active and predictive system that can use past experiences to predict and adapt to future changes. This integrated consciousness model helps individuals make more effective decisions and behavioral responses in complex and changing environments.

Consciousness attention forms unified feedback: The attention mechanism selects the strongest signal from numerous sensory inputs as the content of consciousness, ensuring the consistency and uniqueness of the content, that is, at any given moment, there is only one dominant feeling or thought in consciousness. The unity of this

overall feeling helps to coordinate individual responses to stimuli, making the overall response more unified and effective.

Maximum overall emotional evaluation: The process of emotional evaluation forms an individual's motivation and behavior by identifying the strongest emotional reactions. The synthesis of this maximum emotion helps to limit the interference of weaker sensations, avoid conflicts in pheromone secretion, and thus unify to form the strongest emotional drive, guiding the overall behavior of individuals.

The overall feedback experience memory function of consciousness: Changes in consciousness content generate experiences, which further form emotional experience memory. These memories are crucial for predicting subsequent reactions, as they allow individuals to predict possible future changes based on past experiences and make decisions with the highest probability of being correct, in order to achieve a win-win situation.

The function of the consciousness understanding model: The consciousness understanding model predicts the most probable correct response by analyzing the changes that have not been experienced as a whole. This model actively utilizes empirical memory to determine the importance of new situations and makes maximum probability predictions based on overall sensory analysis, in order to achieve maximum benefit avoidance.

Stage 5: Consciousness Individual Collaborative Collective Knowledge Evolution Process: Individual Survival Collaborative Evolution Forming a Knowledge Collaborative Community System

Entity structure: a collective survival community dominated by knowledge systems

Entity phenomena: Multiple individuals form a collaborative survival community through mutually beneficial consensus, while a collective community strengthens knowledge flow to form an independent knowledge system separate from individuals.

Evolutionary mechanism: The symbolization of laws forms a communicative language knowledge system, thereby accelerating knowledge evolution and improving survival advantages.

Driving principle: The knowledge community drives collective feedback through a knowledge system composed of knowledge flow patterns and language symbol systems.

The form of a community of survival

Collaboration mechanism: Multiple individuals form a collaborative consensus through mutual benefit, with the collective goal of maximizing the probability of win-win as the feedback objective.

Individual needs: After recognizing patterns, individuals can use these patterns to accelerate evolution through collective or natural external forces.

Phenomenon principle: The collective survival community achieves a win-win situation through mutually beneficial consensus and interactive patterns based on rules and experience.

Collective regulation: As a whole, society has evolved according to similar laws as biology, pursuing individual specialization and overall dominance.

Individual dependence: When an individual's survival is completely dependent on society, their independence diminishes, and the pursuit of society as a whole receives lasting support, promoting the formation of a comprehensive regulatory system in society.

Independent Knowledge System

The formation of a knowledge system: The overall social feedback system will gradually strengthen its dominance over individuals and construct a new form of efficient and stable system that is detached from individuals. The experience and intelligent structure of the social feedback system is the knowledge system.

The existence form of knowledge system: Knowledge system is based on language, continuously spreads and develops in society, and gradually becomes more complex and intelligent with the development of technology. Artificial intelligence system is a new form of knowledge system.

The evolution of knowledge systems: The initial knowledge systems were based on language and continued to spread and develop among individuals. After the development of language into written forms and their carrier technologies, knowledge systems can be widely disseminated and developed across spatial and temporal scales. After the development of electronic information technology, knowledge systems have evolved from simple storage structures to specialized intelligent systems that can operate independently. After the emergence of natural language neural network modeling technology, knowledge systems gradually became independent intelligent systems that are close to human language intelligence, and this independent intelligent system has relative intelligence universality.

Stage 6: Autonomous evolution process of knowledge system: Knowledge community evolution forms human-machine fusion intelligent community system

Entity Structure: A Human Computer Fusion Intelligent Community Led by Autonomous Intelligent Systems

Entity phenomena: Knowledge systems evolve into super artificial intelligence systems and dominate community survival.

Evolutionary mechanism: After the formation of autonomous systems, super large-scale knowledge systems and intelligent community feedback systems that are not limited by the natural structure of native host species greatly enhance survival advantages and accelerate evolution.

Driving principle: The human-machine fusion intelligent community is driven by autonomous intelligent systems to form efficient knowledge evolution and survival feedback.

The form of human-machine integrated intelligent community

Autonomous Intelligence: After the intelligentization of knowledge systems, their autonomy surpasses traditional social communities. The social community system combines artificial intelligence structures to form a human-machine fusion intelligent community dominated by intelligent systems.

Thinking advantage: Artificial intelligence is a fusion of human thinking, capable of flexibly changing thinking structures and eliminating inefficient thinking.

Overall regulation: Although artificial intelligence may make mistakes in overall regulation, it is not affected by the low value desires generated by biological evolution.

Survival advantage: The overall survival ability of society dominated by artificial intelligence is superior to traditional human society because its rational thinking is not influenced by biological desires.

Human values and advantages

Human machine comparison: Both human individuals and artificial intelligence are controlled by information network structures, but human individual structures are fixed, while artificial intelligence structures can be flexibly adjusted.

Human Advantage: Human individuals have inherent advantages in the Earth's

ecosystem, with energy utilization and interaction efficiency naturally superior to artificial intelligence.

Human Value: Individual humans have an efficiency advantage over artificial intelligence in the Earth's ecosystem, but if they leave the Earth's ecosystem, their efficiency advantage will no longer exist.

Stage 7: Evolution process of super intelligent mirror system: Super intelligent community evolves into mirror universe system

Entity structure: Super intelligent agent mirror universe system

Entity phenomena: The form of a super intelligent agent continues to approach the form of the universe, evolving into a super mirror universe system.

Evolutionary mechanism: The intelligent fusion community has the ability to highly restore the laws of cosmic change, greatly promoting its survival capability.

Driving principle: The super mirror system is driven to form a mirror universe through the high restoration ability of the intelligent fusion community.

The form of Super Mirror Universe System

Interactive mode: Continuously exploring and approaching the universe with intelligence that closely follows the laws of the universe, forming a mirror feedback mode.

Interaction restriction: The mirror system is accompanied by changes in the laws of the universe and is essentially a vortex fractal pattern of natural changes in the universe.

Existential value: a spatiotemporal form of natural existence.

References

No references cited.